

Ruthenium(II) mediated cleavage of nitrogen-carbon bond : Formation of arene ruthenium(II) dipyridyl NH-ketimine complex

Keisham S. Singh

Bioorganic Chemistry Laboratory, CSIR-National Institute of Oceanography, Dona Paula-403 004, Goa, India

E-mail : keisham@nio.org, keisham.sarjit@gmail.com Fax : 91-832-2450607

Manuscript received online 31 May 2016, accepted 06 September 2016

Abstract : The reaction of $[(\eta^6\text{-arene})\text{RuCl}_2]_2$ with dipyridyl-N-alkylimine ligands, $-(\text{C}_5\text{H}_4\text{N})_2\text{C}=\text{NR}$ in the presence of NH_4PF_6 in refluxing acetonitrile afforded the complexes $[(\eta^6\text{-arene})\text{Ru}\{(\text{C}_5\text{H}_4\text{N})_2\text{C}=\text{NH}\}\text{Cl}]\text{PF}_6$ ($[\text{I}]\text{PF}_6$ - $[\text{3}]\text{PF}_6$) in good yield ($\eta^6\text{-arene} = \eta^6\text{-}p\text{-cymene}, \eta^6\text{-C}_6\text{Me}_6, \eta^6\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6$; $\text{R} = \text{Me}$ or Et). In the complexes, the coordinated dipyridyl ketimine ligand has been transform to $-(\text{C}_5\text{H}_4\text{N})_2\text{C}=\text{NH}$ resulting from nitrogen-carbon bond cleavage of the coordinated ligand. The complexes were isolated as their hexafluorophosphate salts and characterized on the basis of FTIR, ^1H , ^{13}C NMR and partly by ESI-MS spectroscopic data.

Keywords : Ruthenium, dipyridyl ketimine, arene, N-C bond cleavage, spectroscopic data.

Introduction

Current interest on the $(\eta^6\text{-arene})$ ruthenium(II) complexes arises due to their biological properties¹⁻³ and wide applications in catalysis⁴⁻⁶. Indeed arene ruthenium(II) complexes has been used as catalysts for various reactions such as hydrosylation⁷, asymmetric synthesis⁸, metathesis⁹ and more recently Suzuki^{10,11} and Heck^{12,13} type involving C-C bond formation reactions. It is noteworthy that majority of nobel ruthenium complexes displayed an appropriate balance between electronic and steric environment around the metal core. To ensure such an environment, several ligands used such as chloride, carbene or Schiff's bases have been associated with arene, alkylidene or vinylidene¹⁴⁻¹⁶ etc. Moreover, catalytic activity shown by ruthenium complexes is modulated by coordinating ligands. For example, acetate and pyronate forms water soluble ruthenium complexes $[(p\text{-cymene})\text{Ru}(\text{OAc})_2]$ ¹⁷ and $[(p\text{-cymene})\text{Ru}(\text{KA})\text{Cl}]$ ¹⁸ (KA = kojic acid), respectively, which are shown to be efficient catalysts for arylation of heteroarenes in water.

Numerous studied have been reported for synthesis of arene ruthenium(II) compounds, of which complexes with NN donor Schiff's base ligands were most prominent. Specifically, imine ligands containing pyridyl groups have been extensively studied, because of their possibility to

construct a diverse ligands and easily accessible through simple step by condensation of amine with aldehydes or ketones. Notably, imine ligands in metal complexes could undergo carbon-nitrogen bond cleavage either C=N or N-C bonds. Cleavage of C=N bond in imine ligands are commonly observed yielding hydrolysed product. Several reports were appeared for such C=N bond hydrolysis in literature involving Rh¹⁹, Ru²⁰. For instant, Prasad *et al.* observed hydrolysis of C=N bond of imine ligand derived from acetylthiazole in Rh complex¹⁹. Whereas, Geng *et al.* reported C=N bond cleavage and partial hydrolysis of Schiff's base for a ruthenium(II) complex²⁰.

However, cleavage of N-C bond of imine ligand in metal complex is consider unusual and rare although a few examples are known with palladium and ruthenium systems. Albert *et al.* reported the formation of NH aldimine organometallic compound by cleavage of N-C bond in the reaction of palladium acetate and Schiff's base ligand²¹. Further, bridging imine ligand formed complexes involving cleaved of unlikely N-C and N-N bonds upon coordination to the $\text{Ru}(\text{bipy})_2$ core²². Lahiri's group have reported selective cleavage of nitrogen-carbon bond of a diimine ligand in ruthenium complex²³. The above results were indicative that transition metal can mediate nitrogen-carbon bond cleavage of a coordinated imine ligand.

Previously, synthesis of metal complexes bearing dipyriddy-N-alkylimine ligands have been reported for various metals including lithium²⁴, palladium²⁵ and ruthenium²⁶ which gave corresponding dipyriddy-N-alkylimine complexes. Herein, we describes formation of ruthenium(II) dipyriddy-NH-ketimine complexes (**[1]PF₆**-**[3]PF₆**) involving N-C bond cleavage of dipyriddy imine ligand in the reaction of $[(\eta^6\text{-arene})\text{RuCl}_2]_2$ with dipyriddy-N-alkylimine (arene = *p*-cymene, C₆Me₆ or C₆H₆ and dpNMei = dipyriddy-N-methylimine; dpNeti = dipyriddy-N-ethylimine). The complexes were characterized by FT-IR and NMR spectroscopic data (¹H and ¹³C).

Experimental

General remarks : Solvents used were HPLC grade and used as received. RuCl₃·3H₂O was purchased from Arrora Matthey Ltd., India. Methyl amine 2.0 M, ethyl amine 2.0 M solutions and dipyriddyketone were obtained from the Sigma Aldrich Pvt. Ltd. Infrared spectra were obtained in a diffused reflection spectroscopy (DRS) assembly on a Shimadzu-8201PC spectrometer with sample prepared in KBr. NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker 300 MHz spectrometer at 300.13 (¹H), 75.47 MHz (¹³C) with SiMe₄ as internal references and coupling constants were given in Hertz. ESI-MS data were performed on QTOP (MS/MS) Applied Biosystem mass spectrometer. The precursor compound $[(\eta^6\text{-}p\text{-cymene})\text{RuCl}_2]_2$ ^{27,28}, $[(\eta^6\text{-C}_6\text{Me}_6)\text{RuCl}_2]_2$ ²⁹, $[(\eta^6\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6)\text{RuCl}_2]_2$ ²⁷ and the ketimine ligands, dipyriddy-N-methylimine (dpNmei)²² and dipyriddy-N-ethylimine (dpNeti)²⁶ were prepared according to published procedure. The following atoms labelling scheme is used for the ¹H and ¹³C{¹H} NMR spectroscopic data of ligands and *p*-cymene complexes (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Atoms labelling scheme for the pyridyl and *p*-cymene ligands.

Synthesis of complexes :

Preparation of $[(p\text{-cymene})\text{Ru}\{(C_5H_4N)_2C=NH\}\text{-Cl}]\text{PF}_6$ (**[1]PF₆**) :

A mixture of $[(\eta^6\text{-cymene})\text{RuCl}_2]_2$ (0.04 g, 0.065 mmol), NH₄PF₆ (0.023 g, 0.143 mmol) and dpNR (0.143 mmol) were refluxed in acetonitrile for 4 h. The red colour solution was rotary evaporated to dryness and the residue extracted with dichloromethane then filtered. Addition of excess diethyl ether to this filtrate induces a red brown solid. The solid was collected and washed with hexane (2×10 mL), dried in vacuum.

Yield : 0.067 g (86%); FTIR : 3304, 3068, 1687, 840; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, δ) : 12.56 (1H, s), 9.45 (1H, d, *J* 6.0), 8.72 (2H, m), 8.04–8.15 (3H, m), 7.75 (1H, d, *J* 6.4), 7.53 (1H, t, *J* 5.7), 6.15 (1H, d, *J* 5.1), 6.03 (1H, d, *J* 5.7), 5.83 (2H, t, *J* 5.4), 2.73 (sept. 1H), 2.28 (3H, s), 1.15 (3H, d, *J* 6.6), 1.09 (3H, d, *J*_{H-H} 6.9); ¹³C {¹H} NMR (CDCl₃, δ) : 175.26 (C-1), 155.99 (C-7), 153.06 (C-2), 149.52 (C-3), 149.43 (C-8), 138.88 (C-10), 138.54 (C-5), 131.35 (C-6), 128.86 (C-11), 126.87 (C-9), 125.41 (C-4), 106.64 (ring carbons, CPri, *p*-cym), 104.56 (ring carbons, CMe, *p*-cym), 86.09 (t, C_{BB'}), 84.26 (C_{AA'}), 31.26 (CH, CHMe₂), 22.26 (d, CH₃, CHMe₂), 19.00 (s, CH₃, *p*-cym); ESI-MS : *m/z* 453.7375 [M-PF₆]⁺.

Preparation of $[(\eta^6\text{-C}_6\text{Me}_6)\text{Ru}\{(C_5H_4N)_2C=NH\}\text{-Cl}]\text{PF}_6$ (**[2]PF₆**) :

This complex was prepared by following a similar method employed for **[1]PF₆** using $[(\eta^6\text{-C}_6\text{Me}_6)\text{RuCl}_2]_2$ instead of $[(\eta^6\text{-cymene})\text{RuCl}_2]_2$.

Yield : 0.062 g (83%); FTIR : 3321, 3294, 1733, 1638, 1560, 1504, 844; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, δ) : 11.36 (1H, s), 8.98 (1H, d, *J* 5.4), 8.78 (1H, d, *J* 4.2), 8.40 (1H, d, *J* 7.5), 8.05 (3H, m), 7.82 (1H, t, *J* 5.8), 7.57 (1H, t, *J* 5.6), 2.25 (18H, s, C₆Me₆); ¹³C {¹H} NMR (CDCl₃, δ) : 175.03 (C-1), 153.26 (C-7), 153.07 (C-2), 150.32 (C-3), 148.44 (C-8), 139.08 (C-10), 138.53 (C-5), 130.29 (C-6), 128.98 (C-11), 126.97 (C-9), 124.92 (C-4), 96.94 (ring carbons, C₆Me₆), 15.89 (CH₃, C₆Me₆).

Preparation of $[(\eta^6\text{-C}_6\text{H}_6)\text{Ru}\{(C_5H_4N)_2C=NH\}\text{-Cl}]\text{PF}_6$ (**[3]PF₆**) :

A mixture of $[(\eta^6\text{-cymene})\text{RuCl}_2]_2$ (0.04 g, 0.065 mmol), NH₄PF₆ (0.023 g, 0.143 mmol) and dpNR (0.143

mmol) were refluxed in acetonitrile for 4 h. After the reaction, the solvent was rotary evaporated and residue was washed with CH_2Cl_2 then minimum amount of cold methanol. The yellow solid was then washed with diethyl ether (2×10 mL) and dried under vacuum.

Yield : 0.058 g (67%); FTIR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 3315, 3298, 3107, 1733, 1657, 1512, 840; ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6 , δ) : 9.76 (1H, d, J 5.1), 8.85 (1H, d, J 5.4), 8.38 (1H, d, J 8.1), 8.23 (3H, m), 7.96 (1H, m), 7.75 (1H, m), 6.18 (6H, s, C_6H_6); ^{13}C $\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (DMSO- d_6 , δ) : 174.69 (C=N, C-1), 157.31 (C-7), 153.55 (C-2), 150.21 (C-3), 140.06 (C-8), 138.61 (C-10), 130.73 (C-5), 128.91 (C-9), 127.18 (C-4), 125.57 (C-6), 123.45 (C-11), 87.87 (C_6H_6).

Results and discussion

The reaction of $[\{(\eta^6\text{-arene})\text{RuCl}_2\}_2]$ with dpNmei (dpNmei = dipyridyl-N-methylimine) in the presence of NH_4PF_6 in acetonitrile under refluxing condition gave an unexpected dipyridyl-NH-ketimine complexes of formulation $[(\eta^6\text{-arene})\text{Ru}\{(\text{C}_5\text{H}_4\text{N})_2\text{C}=\text{NH}\}\text{Cl}]\text{PF}_6$ (**[1]PF₆**-**[3]PF₆**) (Scheme 1).

In the complexes **[1]PF₆**-**[3]PF₆**, the ligand dipyridyl-N-alkylimine $-(\text{C}_5\text{H}_4\text{N})_2\text{C}=\text{NR}$ was transformed to $-(\text{C}_5\text{H}_4\text{N})_2\text{C}=\text{NH}$ and incorporated to the ruthenium atom by the rare $-(\text{C}_5\text{H}_4\text{N})_2\text{C}=\text{NH}$ fragment arises due to N-C bond cleavage of the imine ligand. The complexes were soluble in water and isolated as their hexafluorophosphate salts in good yields. The coordination of transformed ligand $-(\text{C}_5\text{H}_4\text{N})_2\text{C}=\text{NH}$ in the complex was revealed from the absence of signal at δ 3.92 corresponding to methyl proton of N- CH_3 group in the proton NMR spectra of the complexes²⁴. The proton NMR spectrum of the complexes also exhibited a singlet in the region δ 10–12 assignable to the proton of -NH group of ligand. For instance, complex (**[1]PF₆**) showed a singlet at 12.56 ppm and no signal was observed corresponding to the methyl proton (N- CH_3) of the imine ligand (Fig. 2). The spectrum pattern suggested, the methyl group of the $-(\text{C}_5\text{H}_4\text{N})_2\text{C}=\text{NCH}_3$ (dpNmei) have been transformed to $-(\text{C}_5\text{H}_4\text{N})_2\text{C}=\text{NH}$ and coordinated to the ruthenium forming the complex $[(\eta^6\text{-arene})\text{Ru}\{(\text{C}_5\text{H}_4\text{N})_2\text{C}=\text{NH}\}\text{Cl}]\text{PF}_6$ (**[1]PF₆**). This was further supported from the lack of signal corresponding to

Scheme 1. Reaction pathways for the preparation of complex **[1]PF₆**-**[3]PF₆**.

Fig. 2. ^1H NMR spectrum of complex **[1]PF₆**.

the methyl group (N-CH₃) of imine ligand which was usually appeared at 48 ppm, in the ¹³C NMR spectrum of **[1]PF₆** (see FS2)^{24,26}. Similarly, proton NMR spectra of **[2]PF₆** and **[3]PF₆**, did not showed signal in the region δ 3.92 indicating absent of methyl group (N-CH₃) in the complexes.

The ¹³C NMR spectra of **[1]PF₆**-**[3]PF₆** exhibited signal for C=N carbon at around 175 ppm, while the signals for the ring carbon of η⁶-*p*-cymene, η⁶-C₆Me₆ and η⁶-C₆H₆ were appeared around δ 84.25–77.49, 96.94 and 87.48, respectively. In the case of **[2]PF₆** and **[3]PF₆**, the ¹H NMR spectrum showed a strong singlet at δ 2.25 and 5.94, assignable to the methyl proton of coordinated η⁶-C₆Me₆ and η⁶-C₆H₆ ligands, respectively. As observed for **[1]PF₆**, the ¹³C NMR spectra of **[2]PF₆** and **[3]PF₆** did not showed signal corresponding to methyl group (N-CH₃) indicating the coordination of transform ligand -(C₅H₄N)₂C=NH. Infrared spectra of **[1]PF₆**-**[3]PF₆** showed absorption peak in the region 3304–3321 cm⁻¹ due to N-H bond of the coordinated imine fragment³⁰. In addition, the infrared spectra of the compounds display absorption band in the region 1638–1687 cm⁻¹ assignable to C=N stretching frequency^{31,32}. In all these compounds, a strong absorption band appeared in the region 840 cm⁻¹ have been assigned to PF₆ counterion. The ESI-MS spectral data of the complex **[1]PF₆** showed peak at *m/z* 453.7375 due to [M-PF₆]⁺. Spectroscopic data of the compounds are well matched with the formulation of compounds **[1]PF₆**-**[3]PF₆** and data suggest cleavage of N-CH₃ bond of dipyriddy-N-ketimine ligand and coordination of transform ligand -(C₅H₄N)₂C=NH to the ruthenium centre.

Under similar condition [{(η⁶-arene)RuCl₂}₂] react with -(C₅H₄N)₂C=N-C₂H₅ to give identical compound **[1]PF₆**-**[3]PF₆** (Scheme 1).

When the reaction of [RuCl₂(*p*-cymene)]₂ with dpNmei or dpNeti was performed at room temperature, ruthenium(II) dipyriddy-NH-ketimine compound (**[1]PF₆**) was formed along with dipyriddy-N-alkylimine compounds (**[4]PF₆**-**[5]PF₆**) (Scheme 2). The formation of mixture of compounds was evident from spectroscopic data. For instance, the reaction of [RuCl₂(*p*-cymene)]₂ with -(C₅H₄N)₂C=N-C₂H₅ (dpNeti) at room temperature gave a yellow solid. ¹H NMR spectrum showed peak at δ 12.45 assignable to the -NH group and at δ 3.52 due to methylene (-CH₂-) of the coordinated -(C₅H₄N)₂C=N-C₂H₅ ligand. Spectrum suggest the presence of both compounds **[1]PF₆** and **[5]PF₆**. This was further supported by ESI-MS analysis which gave intense peak at around *m/z* 453.7375 corresponding to (M-PF₆)⁺ of **[1]PF₆** and at *m/z* 481.7842 due to (M-PF₆)⁺ of **[5]PF₆**. We did not attempt to isolate the compounds **[4]PF₆** and **[5]PF₆** from the mixture as these compounds were already reported in our earlier communication²⁶. Recently, a similar N-C bond cleavage of imine ligand (-N-R) was found in the reaction of [RhCl₂(η⁵-C₅Me₅)]₂ with dipyriddy-N-alkylimine ligand, -(C₅H₄N)₂C=N-R where the transform ligand -(C₅H₄N)₂C=N-H coordinated to the rhodium centre to give rhodium(III) dipyriddy-NH-ketimine compound, [(η⁵-C₅Me₅)Rh{(C₅H₄N)₂C=N-H}]⁺³³. The identity of [(η⁵-C₅Me₅)Rh{(C₅H₄N)₂C=N-H}]⁺ was established by spectroscopic data as well as by single crystal X-ray diffraction³³.

Scheme 2. Reaction pathways for the formation of dipyriddy-NH-ketimine and dipyriddy-N-alkylimine complexes.

Notably, in transition metal complexes, cleavage of C=N group of imine ligands is commonly observed. Such cleavage of C=N group of imine ligand was recently reported by Prasad *et al.*, during the crystallization of the complex $[(\eta^5\text{-Cp}^*)\text{Rh}(\text{ata})\text{Cl}]$ (ata = 2-acetylthioazine) due to hydrolysis of the ligand¹⁹. In contrast, bond cleavage involving N-C bonds of ligands are rare and unlikely except a few report available for metal complexes of Pd²¹, Ru^{22,23} and Rh³³. Further N-C bond cleavage is not restricted only to Schiff's bases, the cleavage have also seen in other system such as ferrocene. Zhang *et al.* observed such an N-C bond cleavage involving cleavage of nitrogen-alkyl bond (-NR₂) to give -NHR in palladium catalysed reaction of FcCH₂NMe₂ with diphenylacetylene (Fc = ferrocene), where one of the methyl group of FcCH₂NMe₂ get degraded and formed a sub product FcCH₂NHMe³⁴.

Above results showed that N-C bond clavage could be promoted by various transition metals. N-C bond cleavage is influence by solvent employed to some extend. Lahiri's group observed formation of a mononuclear ruthenium NH-imine compound involving N-C bond cleavage during the reaction of [Ru(bipy)] with a bridging imine ligand when the reacton was performed in acetonitrile in presence of water. In contrast, when the same reaction was performed in ethanol gave a dinuclear ruthenium N-alkyl imine compound with no N-C bond cleavage²¹. The present study demonstrated that ruthenium(II) species could mediate transformation of -NR group of a coordinated dipyridyl ketimine ligands to dipyridyl-NH ketimine ligand through an unlikely N-C bond cleavage to generate ruthenium(II) dipyridyl-NH-ketimine complexes.

Conclusion

This paper describes formation of ruthenium(II) dipyridyl-NH-ketimine compound (**[1]PF₆-[3]PF₆**) during the reaction of [RuCl₂(arene)]₂ with dipyridyl-N-ketimine ligand -(C₅H₄N)₂C=NR. In this NH-ketimine compounds (**[1]PF₆-[3]PF₆**), the rare transform ligand -(C₅H₄N)₂C=NH was coordinated to the ruthenium atom. The transform ligand was formed as a result of N-C bond cleavage of coordinated ketimine ligand. The present study showed organoruthenium(II) could transform methyl or

ethyl group (-NR) of coordinated ketimine ligand to -NH ketimine via N-C bond cleavage to form ruthenium(II) NH-ketimine compounds.

Acknowledgement

KSS is graterful to the Department of Science and Technology (Grant no. SR/FT/CS-001/2010) for financial support and Director, NIO for providing facility.

References

1. Y. K. Yan, M. Melchart, A. Habtemariam and P. J. Sadler, *Chem. Commun.*, 2005, 4764.
2. F. Wang, J. Bella, J. A. Parkinson and P. J. Sadler, *J. Biol. Inorg. Chem.*, 2005, **10**, 147.
3. T. Bugarcic, A. Habtemariam, J. Stepankova, P. Heringova, J. Kasparkova, R. J. Deeth, R. D. L. Johnstone, A. Prescimone, A. Parkin, S. Parsons, V. Brabec and P. J. Sadler, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2008, **47**, 11470.
4. C. S. Allardyce, P. J. Dyson, D. J. Ellis, P. A. Salter and R. Scopelliti, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 2003, **668**, 35.
5. H. Horvath, G. Laurency and A. Katho, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 2004, **689**, 1036.
6. Y. Na and S. Chang, *Org. Lett.*, 2000, **2**, 1887.
7. B. Li, C. B. Bheeter, C. Darcel and P. H. Dixneuf, *ACS Catal.*, 2011, **1**, 1221.
8. K. Mashima, T. Hino and H. Takaya, *Dalton Trans.*, 1992, 2099.
9. R. Castarlenas, C. Vovard, C. Fischmeister and P. H. Dixneuf, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2006, **128**, 409.
10. Y. Na, S. Park, S. B. Han, H. Han, S. Ko and S. Chang, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2004, **126**, 250.
11. R. K. Chinnagolla and M. Jeganmohan, *Org. Lett.*, 2012, **14**, 5246.
12. S. Oi, K. Sakai and Y. Inoue, *Org. Lett.*, 2005, **18**, 4009.
13. P. B. Arockiam, C. Fischmeister, C. Bruneau and P. H. Dixneuf, *Green Chem.*, 2011, **13**, 3075.
14. T. Weskamp, W. C. Schattenmann, M. Spiegler and W. A. Herrmann, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 1998, **37**, 2490.
15. L. Ackermann, A. Fürstner, T. Weskamp, F. J. Kohl and W. A. Herrmann, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1999, **40**, 4787.
16. A. K. Chatterjee, J. P. Morgan, M. Scholl and R. H. Grubbs, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2000, **122**, 3783.
17. P. B. Arockiam, C. Fischmeister, C. Bruneau and P. H. Dixneuf, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2010, **49**, 6629.
18. K. S. Singh and P. H. Dixneuf, *ChemCatChem.*, 2013, **9**, 21.

19. K. T. Prasad, G. Gupta, A. V. Rao, B. Das and K. M. Rao, *Polyhedron*, 2009, **28**, 2649.
20. J. Geng, K. Zhang, Y. X. Peng, L. Wang and W. Huang, *Inorg. Chem. Commun.*, 2014, **40**, 112.
21. J. Albert, J. M. Cadena, A. González, J. Granell, X. Solans and M. Font-Bardia, *Chem. Commun.*, 2003, 528.
22. S. Chakraborty, B. Mondal, B. Sarkar and G. K. Lahiri, *J. Chem. Sci.*, 2002, **114**, 443.
23. S. Chakraborty, M. G. Walawalkar and G. K. Lahiri, *Polyhedron*, 2003, **20**, 1851.
24. B. F. Chávez, B. A. M. Ortega, J. G. A. Rodriguez and N. A. López, *J. Chem. Cryst.*, 2005, **35**, 451.
25. N. A. López, J. G. A. Rodríguez, S. G. Montel, M. E. P. Hernández, C. A. G. Vindal and A. J. Pérez, *ARKIVOC*, 2008, 43.
26. K. S. Singh and W. Kaminsky, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 2011, **365**, 487.
27. M. A. Bennett and A. K. Smith, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1974, 233.
28. M. A. Bennett, T. W. Matheson, G. B. Robertson, A. K. Smith and P. A. Tucker, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1980, **10**, 1014.
29. M. A. Bennett, T. N. Huang, T. W. Matheson, G. B. Robertson and A. K. Smith, *Inorg. Synth.*, 1985, **21**, 75.
30. J. R. Dyer, "Application of Absorption Spectroscopy of Organic Compounds", Prentice-Hall, New Delhi, 1989, 37.
31. R. H. Molina and A. Mederos in : J. A. McCleverty and T. J. Meyer (eds.), "Acyclic and Macrocyclic Schiff Base Ligands in Comprehensive Coordination Chemistry II", Vol. 2, Pergamon Press, New York, 2004, 411.
32. P. A. Vigato and S. Tanburini, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 2004, **248**, 1717.
33. K. S. Singh, P. Wang and Y. Mozharivskiy, Unpublished results.
34. H. Zhang, X. Cui, X. Yao, H. Wang, J. Zhang and Y. Wu, *Org. Lett.*, 2012, **14**, 2925.